

3" PMTs for the Hyper-K outer detector

Hyper-Kamiokande is a next generation water Cherenkov detector
 Optically split into inner and outer detector separated by Tyvek
 Outer detector serves as veto for cosmic rays and aids event selection

Outer Detector PMTs

- ~3600 waterproofed 3" Photomultiplier Tubes (PMTs)
- Two candidate PMTs – Hamamatsu and NNVT (tendering in progress)
- Wavelength-shifting (WLS) plates to expand photo-coverage
- Walls lined with reflective Tyvek
- Main requirements:
 - Waterproof and resistant to 10 bar pressure
 - Low dark rate (< 2 kHz at 25°)
 - High quantum efficiency across Cherenkov spectrum
 - Good collection efficiency at high angles

Photo of the Super-K outer detector
 (Hyper-K PMTs are smaller and more spread out)

Outer detector PMT measurements

Charge and noise

- ~400 nm LED with both single and multi-photoelectron intensity
- Gain and dark rate dependence on input voltage
- Charge and time resolution, peak-to-valley ratio
- Long-term measurements of gain and dark rate stability

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Angular dependence

- Variation of single photoelectron light yield and relative detection efficiency
- Robotic arm rotates 405 nm LED light around surface of the PMT
- Positional precision ~2 mm
- Single and multi-photoelectron response
- Light yield measured with SiPM

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Detected ~10% variation of PMT response aligned with the dynode system

See poster #C3 for further details

PMT + WLS plate

- Variations in PMT and the WLS plate
 - Scan surface of plate and PMT with a 285 nm UV LED
 - Independently rotate PMT and WLS plate by 90° and repeat
- Fit results and separate effects of:
- 1) Radial distance from PMT
 - 2) Inhomogeneities in WLS plate
 - 3) Variation in PMT collection efficiency
 - 4) Inhomogeneities of the setup
- Confirmed ~10% variation of PMT collection efficiency aligned with the dynode system

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 Fire on center of photocathode
 Fire on WLS

Single photon detection efficiency

- Inject light at 5 positions: PMT and 4 corners of the WLS plate
 - 4 LED wavelengths: 275, 315, 365, and 405 nm
 - Relative comparison between two PMT vendors
- Confirmed higher detection efficiency of Hamamatsu PMT at lower wavelengths

Underwater & pressure

- Short and long-term measurement under water in 10 bar pressure with signal readout
 - Undersea implosion test at Hokkaido and Mallorca
 - Down to 80 m under sea level
 - Outer detector PMT on a frame with 20" PMTs
 - Controlled implosion of central 20" PMT
- All outer detector PMTs passed implosion test

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